

Synthesis of Monochlorotriazinyl Reactive Dyes from 1-Naphthol-7-amino-3-sulphonic Acid and their Application

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The monochlorotriazinyl reactive system is of major commercial importance in reactive dyeing¹. Recently it has been used extensively in conjugation with sulphatoethylsulphones to give the first mixed bifunctional reactive dyes².

In view of the encouraging reports about the technical application of some of the dyes based on amino naphthol sulphonic acid³, we report here the synthesis and study of the dyeing properties of the monochlorotriazinyl reactive dyes based on 1-naphthol-7-amino-3-sulphonic acid having the following general formula.

Results and Discussion

1-Naphthol-7-(2',4'-dichloro-*s*-triazin-6'-ylamino)-3-sulphonic acid (synthesised by condensing 1-naphthol-7-amino-3-sulphonic acid with cyanuric chloride) was coupled in alkaline medium with 2-aminonaphthalene-1,5-disulphonic acid to give 1-naphthol-2-(1',5'-disulphonaphthyl-2'-azo)-7-(2'',4''-dichloro-*s*-triazin-6''-ylamino)-3-sulphonic acid, which on further condensation with various arylureas gave the monochlorotriazinyl reactive dyes (**1-14**; yields 68-86%). These dyes were purified either by dissolution in DMF and reprecipitation with acetone or by dialysis in

deionised water and also by preparative thin layer chromatography using benzyl alcohol-DMF-water (3 : 2 : 2) solvent system and silica gel G as absorbent : **1** (R = H), m.p. 290°; **2** (R = *o*-CH₃), 282°; **3** (R = *m*-CH₃), 270°; **4** (R = *p*-CH₃), 258°; **5** (R = *o*-OCH₃), 242°; **6** (R = *m*-OCH₃), 274°; **7** (R = *p*-OCH₃), 260°; **8** (R = *o*-NO₂), 258°; **9** (R = *m*-NO₂), 278°; **10** (R = *p*-NO₂), 284°; **11** (R = *o*-Cl), 253°; **12** (R = *m*-Cl), 294°; **13** (R = *p*-Cl), 289°; **14** (R = Br), 285°.

The absorption spectra (Hitachi U-3200) of all the dyes (**1-14**) in aqueous solutions at 28° revealed λ_{\max} in the range 485-505 nm. Ir spectra (KBr) of 1-naphthol-2-(1',5'-disulphonaphthyl-2'-azo)-7-(2''-aryluroido-4''-chloro-*s*-triazin-6''-ylamino)-3-sulphonic acid dyes revealed characteristic bands at 810-825 (C₃H₃), 1 170-1 185 (S=O), 1 560-1 580 (N=N), 1 600-1 635 (NH) and 3 300-3 340 cm⁻¹ (NHCONH).

Their pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) showed signals at δ 1.99 (3H, CH₃), 3.83 (3H, OCH₃), 6.9 (1H, OH), 7.3 (1H, NH), 8.8 (1H, NHCO) and 6.6-7.4 (ArH).

Application : All the dyes were applied to viscose rayon, wool and silk fabrics in 2% shade according to the following general procedure.

The sample of the fabric (2 g) was introduced at room temperature in the dye-bath containing

at room temperature in the dye-bath containing the following materials : dye, 40 mg; Glauber salt (20%), 1 ml; formic acid (10%) (for wool and silk only), 1 ml; soda ash (10%) (for viscose rayon only), 5 ml. The temperature of the bath was gradually raised to 100° in 15 min. The pH for viscose rayon was adjusted to 7.5–8.0 by adding soda ash solution and for wool and silk it was adjusted to 4.5–5.0 by adding formic acid solution, and a liquor ratio for all the fabrics was maintained to 20:1. The fabric was worked up in the dye-bath for 1 h. The dyeing was terminated by removing the fabric from dye-bath and stirred it into water (40 ml). The fabric was then removed squeezed and rinsed with water (50 ml) and resqueezed.

Evidence for chemical bonding between the dyes and fibres : The following are the indirect evidence obtained for the establishment of a covalent bond between the dye and the fabric. The dyed samples of fabric retained the colour after boiling with (i) isopropanol, (ii) *o*-chlorophenol and chloroform at 102° for 10 min, (iii) 25% aqueous pyridine at room temperature for 24 h. Polyvinylalcohol may be regarded as similar in nature to viscose rayon from

the point of view of reactivity. If aqueous solutions of polyvinylalcohol, on one hand a reactive dye and, on the other, an acid dye, were poured on to the surface of a solution of caustic soda saturated with salt, a film it was formed. The film containing the reactive dye can subsequently be boiled with water. It was found that the film was not disintegrated but it swelled somewhat, whereas the film containing on acid dye rapidly dissolved. The colour of the reactive dyes is due to the presence of an azo group. Consequently this dye can be reduced on the fibre by sodium hydrosulphite to two amine-containing products. If the dye reacted with fibre before reduction, one of these products should remain anchored to the fibre and should resist washing out. Such a 'discharged' fibre can in fact be diazotised and coupled with another phenol or amine to produce a new dye, and this process can be repeated indefinitely. Again this is very strong evidence to show that the monochlorotriazinyl reactive dye is combined with the fibre.

Exhaustion study of dyes : The percentage exhaustion study of the dyes was performed using the standard procedure. The results are given in Table 1. It was observed that the

TABLE 1

Compd. no.	Colour on dyed fibre	λ_{max} nm	R_f value	K/S value			% Exhaustion			Light fastness			Wash fastness			Rubbing fastness						
				V	W	S	V	W	S	V	W	S	V	W	S	Dry			Wet			
1	Reddish pink	490	0.78	0.636	0.661	0.692	73	54	50	4	4	5	4	4-5	4-5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
2	Red	505	0.83	0.557	0.644	0.654	76	57	62	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	4	5	5	4	5	
3	Red	500	0.80	0.563	0.651	0.664	75	51	49	4-5	5	4-5	3-4	4	3-4	4	5	4-5	5	5	5	
4	Red	505	0.76	0.559	0.651	0.660	78	52	64	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	5	5	5	
5	Reddish pink	490	0.79	0.630	0.637	0.634	72	61	62	3-4	3	3	4	4-5	4	3-4	4	4	3-4	4	4	
6	Reddish pink	490	0.70	0.634	0.642	0.674	70	60	61	3	3	3	4	3-4	4	3	4	4	3-4	3-4	4	
7	Reddish pink	505	0.84	0.545	0.631	0.654	75	60	59	3	3-4	3-4	4	4	4	4	3	3	4	4	4	
8	Light red	485	0.80	0.612	0.685	0.669	81	56	58	4	4-5	5	4	5	5	5	3-4	3	4	4	4	
9	Light red	480	0.72	0.597	0.623	0.639	71	55	60	4-5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	
10	Light red	465	0.80	0.610	0.635	0.670	73	58	69	4	5	5	4-5	5	5	4-5	5	5	5	5	5	
11	Dark red	500	0.74	0.545	0.598	0.617	71	65	63	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4-5	5	5	
12	Dark red	490	0.75	0.619	0.637	0.669	70	63	58	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	
13	Dark red	505	0.75	0.541	0.541	0.636	72	61	57	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	
14	Dark red	490	0.83	0.627	0.647	0.674	75	56	52	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	

V = Viscose rayon, W = Wool, S = Silk

percentage exhaustion on viscose rayon is good to excellent and on wool and silk moderate to good. The introduction of a substituent in monochlorotriazinyl reactive dyes causes better exhaustion, but differences arise from the nature and position of the substituent. No proper generalisation is possible within the series of dyes.

Shade : The reactive dyes gave generally red hues with good levelness, brightness and depth on all the three fibres. The results are given in Table 1.

Evaluation of K/S value : The K/S value was evaluated for all the dyed samples by computer colour matching system (Table 1) using the equation,

$$K/S = (1-R)^2/2R$$

where *K* is the coefficient of absorption, *S* the coefficient of scattering and *R* the reflectance.

Fastness tests : Data on fastness properties (Table 1) show that the light fastness is from moderate to good for all the fibres. The dyes show a remarkable fading or photodegradation on dyed fibres. However, improvement in this property is observed for the nitro, chloro and bromo substituted dyes. The fastness to washing and rubbing is good to excellent for all the fibres. This indicates good substantivity, good penetration and affinity of these dyes for the fibres.

Experimental

All the m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Varian EM 360L (90 MHz) spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard. Elemental analysis was performed on a Carlo-Erba 1108 analyser.

1-Naphthol-7-(2',4'-dichloro-s-triazin-6'-ylamino)-3-sulphonic acid : A nearly neutral solution of 1-naphthol-7-amino-3-sulphonic acid (2.93 g,

0.01 mol) in sodium carbonate solution (10%, w/v) was added to a well-stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (1.84 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone, maintaining the temperature at 0–5°. The mixture was adjusted to pH 7 and stirred for 3 h. A clear solution obtained was used for the subsequent coupling reaction.

Diazonium chloride of 2-amino naphthalene-1,5-disulphonic acid : 2-Amino naphthalene-1,5-disulphonic acid (3.04 g, 0.01 mol) was diazotised in the usual manner. The resulting diazo solution was used for subsequent coupling reaction.

Coupling of diazo solution with 1-naphthol-7-(2',4'-dichloro-s-triazin-6'-ylamino)-3-sulphonic acid : Diazo solution was added to the clear solution of 1-naphthol-7-(2',4'-dichloro-s-triazin-6'-ylamino)-3-sulphonic acid dropwise with stirring maintaining neutral pH by addition of Na_2CO_3 solution (10%, w/v). The stirring was continued for 3 h at 0–5°. NaCl (10%, w/v) was then added to it with stirring and the resulting solid was washed with small amount of NaCl (5%, w/v) and used for subsequent reaction.

1-Naphthol-2-(1',5'-disulphonaphthyl-2'-azo)-7-(2'',4''-dichloro-s-triazin-6''-ylamino)-3-sulphonic acid. General method : Aryl urea (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone was added dropwise for 1.5 h to a stirred solution of 1-naphthol-2-(1',5'-disulphonaphthyl-2'-azo)-7-(2'',4''-dichloro-s-triazin-6''-ylamino)-3-sulphonic acid (7.67 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone at 35°. The temperature was gradually increased to 45° during 2 h and the pH maintained at 7 by aqueous sodium carbonate solution. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature, and the resulting solid dye was washed with small amount of NaCl (5%, w/v) and purified from DMF-acetone solution.

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